

A REVIEW ON RASACHANDRODAYA-A UNIQUE AYURVEDIC FORMULATION

Dr. Chethan D.^{1*}, Dr. Laxmibai Kurle²

Final Year PG Scholar^{1*}, Professor²,

*^{1,2}Dept. of PG Studies In Rasashastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana, Taranath Govt. Ayurvedic Medical College and Hospital Ballari.

Article Received on 06 Nov. 2025,
Article Revised on 26 Nov. 2025,
Article Published on 01 Dec. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17812049>

*Corresponding Author

Dr. Chethan D.

Final Year PG Scholar, Dept. of PG Studies In Rasashastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana, Taranath Govt. Ayurvedic Medical College and Hospital Ballari.

How to cite this Article: Dr. Chethan D.^{1*}, Dr. Laxmibai Kurle². (2025). A REVIEW ON RASACHANDRODAYA-A UNIQUE AYURVEDIC FORMULATION. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 14(12), 1080-1087.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Rasashastra is a specialized branch of Ayurveda focused primarily on *Parada* and its various formulations. Mercury is commonly combined with other metals, minerals, and herbal substances to create medicinal preparations. When *Parada* is processed along with metals and minerals, the resulting formulations are known as *Rasarasayana* (herbo-mineral preparations). There are four main types of *Rasarasayana*: *Khalviya*, *Parpati*, *Kupipakva*, and *Pottali Kalpa*. *Rasachandrodaya*^[1] is one such unique *Khalviya* formulation having ingredients like *Rasakarpura*, *Shuddha Gandhaka*, *Shuddha Haratala*, *Shuddha Jayapala*, *Shuddha Vatsanabha*, *Trikatu*, *Triphala*, *Mulaka* indicated in conditions like *Bhayankara Kushta*, *Prameha*, *Kshaya*, *Gulma*, *Shoola*, *Malajeerna*, *Bhrama*, *Kanthashoola*, *Jwara*, *Sannipata*, *Visuchika*, *Vishama Jwara*. Therefore, it is crucial to explore formulations like *Rasachandrodaya* to understanding its role

and to incorporate in treatment becomes essential.

KEYWORDS: *Rasachandrodaya*, *Rasashastra*, *Rasakarpoora*, *Khalviya*, Herbomineral.

INTRODUCTION

Rasachandrodaya^[1] is a unique *Kharaliya* formulation mentioned in *Rasayoga Sagara*. The name *Rasachandrodaya* is derived from Sanskrit words *Rasa*(parada) and *Chandrodaya* (rise

of moon) Just as the moon rises to dispel darkness, this formulation helps dispel diseases and promotes health and longevity.

Rasa Chandrodaya is unique *Kharaliya* formulation having ingredients like *Rasakarpura*, *Shuddha Gandhaka*, *Shuddha Haratala*, *Shuddha Vatsanabha*, *Shuddha Jayapala*, *Trikatu*, *Triphala*, *Mulaka* along with bhavana Dravya like *gomutra* further enhancing therapeutic properties. It is indicated in conditions like *Bhayankara Kushta*, *Prameha*, *Kshaya*, *Gulma*, *Shoola*, *Malajeerna*, *Bhrama*, *Kanta shoola*, *Jwara*, *Sannipata*, *Visuchika*, *Vishama Jwara*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The reference for *Rasachandrodaya* was taken from *Rasayoga Sagara (Dwitiya Bhaga)*. Sections about the preparation, properties, and uses of the medicines were carefully studied and documented.

Table no. 1: Showing Ingredients of Rasachandrodaya.

Sl. No.	Ingredients	Chemical / Botanical Name	Quantity
1	<i>Rasa Karpura</i> ^[2]	Mercuric Chloride (HgCl ₂)	1Tola
2	<i>Shuddha Gandhaka</i> ^[3]	Purified Sulphur	1tola
3	<i>Shuddha Haratala</i> ^[4]	Arsenic Trisulphide (As ₂ S ₃)	1tola
4	<i>Shuddha Vatsanabha</i> ^[5]	Aconitum ferox	1tola
5	<i>Shuddha Tankana</i> ^[6]	Borax (Sodium Borate – Na ₂ B ₄ O ₇ ·10H ₂ O)	6masha
6	<i>Shuddha Jayapala</i> ^[7]	Croton tiglium	6masha
7	<i>Triphala</i>	Combination of <i>Emblica officinalis</i> (<i>Amalaka</i>), <i>Terminalia chebula</i> (<i>Haritaki</i>), and <i>Terminalia bellerica</i> (<i>Vibhitaki</i>)	3masha
8	<i>Trikatu</i>	Combination of <i>Zingiber officinale</i> (<i>Shunthi</i>), <i>Piper longum</i> (<i>Pippali</i>), and <i>Piper nigrum</i> (<i>Maricha</i>)	3masha
9.	<i>Mulaka</i>	<i>Raphanus sativus</i>	3masha
10.	<i>Gomutra</i>	<i>Bos taurus</i>	Quantity sufficient for bhavana.

METHOD OF PREPARATION AS PER RASAYOGA SAGARA

- *Rasakarpura*, *Shuddha Gandhaka*, *Shuddha Haratala*, and *Shuddha Vatsanabha* were taken in a quantity of 1 tola each in a clean *Khalva Yantra*.

- *Shuddha Tankana* and *Shuddha Jayapala* powders were then added in the amount of 6 Masha each.
- To this mixture, *Triphala Churna*, *Trikatu Churna*, and dried *Mulaka Churna* were incorporated in the quantity of 3 Masha each and triturated thoroughly to form a homogeneous mixture.
- Subsequently, a sufficient quantity of *Gomutra* was added, and trituration was continued until the mixture was suitable for vati preparation. Vatis of 1 Ratti each were then formed and stored in an airtight container.

Anupana: *Vyadhianusara*

Mathra-1 Ratti

Indications: *Bhayankara Kushta, Prameha, Kshaya, Gulma, Shoola, Malajeerna, Bhrama, Kantha shoola, Jwara, Sannipata, Visuchika, Vishama Jwara.*

Table no. 2: Showing the Properties of Ingredients of Rasachandrodaya.

Sl. no.	Name	Rasa	Guna	Virya	Vipaka	Karma
01	<i>Rasa Karpura</i> ^[2]	<i>Tikta, Kashaya</i>	<i>Laghu, Tikshna</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Krimighna, Jantughna, Lekhana, Shodhana, Stambhana</i>
02	<i>Shuddha Gandhaka</i> ^[3]	<i>Madhura, Tikta, Kashaya</i>	<i>Snigdha, Picchila, Laghu</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Krimighna, Rasayana, Vranaropaka, Kushtaghna</i>
03	<i>Shuddha Haratala</i> ^[4]	<i>Tikta, Kashaya</i>	<i>Laghu, Tikshna</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Kushtaghna, Shothahara, Lekhana, Kaphaghna, Rasayana</i>
04	<i>Shuddha Vatsanabha</i> ^[5]	<i>Tikta, Katu</i>	<i>Laghu, Tikshna, Ruksha</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Shoolahara, Vedanashamaka, Jwaraghna, Vatakaphahara</i>
05	<i>Shuddha Tankana</i> ^[6]	<i>Lavana</i>	<i>Laghu, Tikshna</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Kasahara, Shothahara, Lekhana, Kaphavatahara</i>
06	<i>Shuddha Jayapala</i> ^[7]	<i>Tikta, Katu</i>	<i>Tikshna, Ruksha</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Virechaka, Krimighna, Bhedana</i>
07	<i>Amalaki</i> ^[8]	<i>Amla pradhana Lavana vargita pancharasa</i>	<i>Laghu, Ruksha</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Rasayana, Chakshushya, Pittahara, Deepana, Vayasthapana</i>
08	<i>Haritaki</i> ^[9]	<i>Kashaya pradhana lavana vargita pancharasa</i>	<i>Laghu, Ruksha</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Vatanulomana, Rasayana, Medhya, Shothahara, Rechana</i>
09	<i>Bibhitaki</i> ^[10]	<i>Kashaya (dominant), Madhura, Tikta</i>	<i>Laghu, Ruksha</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Kaphaghna, Kasahara, Rasayana, Bhedana, Netrahita</i>
10	<i>Shunthi</i> ^[11]	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Laghu, Snigdha</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Deepana, Pachana,</i>

						<i>Vatanulomana, Shothahara, Kaphaghna</i>
11	Pippali ^[12]	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Laghu, Snigdha</i>	<i>Anushna (Mildly Ushna)</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Deepana, Rasayana, Vatanulomana, Shwasahara, Agnivardhaka</i>
12	Maricha ^[13]	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Laghu, Tikshna, Ruksha</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Deepana, Pachana, Krimighna, Kaphaghna, Srotoshodhaka</i>
13	Mulaka ^[14]	<i>Katu, Tikta</i>	<i>Laghu, Tikshna, Snigdha</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Deepana, pachana, Shothahara, Mutrala, Bhedana</i>
14	Gomutra ^[15]	<i>Katu, Madhura</i>	<i>Laghu, Tikshna, Ruksha</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Agnideepana, Lekhana, Shodhana, Krimighna, Medohara, Mutrala, and Vishaghna.</i>

Probable Mode of Action of *Rasachandrodaya*

Rasachandrodaya is a classical Ayurvedic herbo-mineral formulation described in *Rasayoga Sagara*, indicated in conditions like *Bhayankara Kushta, Prameha, Kshaya, Gulma, Shoola, Malajeerna, Bhrama, Kantha shoola, Jwara, Sannipata, Visuchika, Vishama Jwara* managing chronic disorders involving deep-seated *dosha dushti, srotorodha, and aamajanya vikara*. The formulation integrates purified *Rasoushadhis*, herbal powders, and *Gomutra* as a *Bhavana dravya*, enhancing both the bioavailability and therapeutic efficacy of the constituents.

The presence of *Trikatu, Triphala, and Mulaka* contributes significantly to the formulation's ability to stimulate digestive fire and facilitate the breakdown of *aama*. These ingredients possess *Deepana and Pachana* properties, which are essential in correcting *mandagni* (low digestive capacity), a key etiological factor in many chronic ailments such as *Gulma, Malajeerna, and shoola*.

Combination of *Rasa Karpura (mercuric chloride), Shuddha Haratala (arsenic trisulfide), and Gandhaka (sulphur)* exert strong *shodhana* (purifying) and *lekhana* (scraping) effects, particularly targeting the *raktavaha and medovaha srotas*. These agents are known for their *tikshna, ushna, and sookshma* properties, facilitating the removal of metabolic waste and excess *kapha* from deeper tissues.

Ingredients like *Shuddha Vatsanabha and Shuddha Jayapala*, when properly processed, offer *vishaghna and krimighna* effects. Their potent action helps neutralize internal toxins and

supports the management of disorders like *visuchika*, *jwara*, and *kushta*, where microbial or toxin overload is implicated.

Herbal constituents such as *Haritaki*, *Amalaki*, and *Pippali* contribute rasayana (rejuvenative) effects, supporting *dhatu poshana* and promoting *ojas*. These ingredients assist in cellular regeneration, making *Rasachandrodaya* useful in conditions like *kshaya* (tissue depletion), chronic fever, and general debility.

The use of *Gomutra* (cow's urine) as the *bhavana* dravya plays a crucial role in enhancing the formulation's pharmacokinetic profile. Its *Yogavahi* (bioenhancer) property ensures deeper tissue penetration of the active principles. Additionally, its inherent *Lekhana*, *Mutrala*, and *aama Pachana* qualities contribute to *Srotoshodhaka* (channel purification), particularly within *raktavaha*, *mamsavaha*, and *medovaha* systems.

The overall pharmacodynamic profile of *Rasachandrodaya* suggests a predominant action on *kapha* and *vata* doshas, with selective regulation of *pitta*. Through its combined *Ushna*, *Tikshna*, and *Katu-vipaka* nature, the formulation helps restore *doshic* balance, clears obstruction in body channels, and supports systemic detoxification and rejuvenation.

DISCUSSION

Rasachandrodaya is a unique classical herbo-mineral formulation that combines potent *Rasoushadhis*, purified minerals, and digestive-supportive herbs to address a wide range of chronic conditions rooted in *Aama*, *Srotorodha*, and *Dosha-vikriti*. The synergistic action of metallic elements like *Rasa Karpura*, *Shuddha Gandhaka*, and *Shuddha Haratala*, when processed with *Gomutra Bhavana*, creates a formulation with powerful *Deepana*, *Shodhana*, *Kṛmighna*, and *Lekhana* properties. These actions make it particularly effective in conditions involving chronic inflammation, metabolic imbalance, and toxin accumulation.

Rasa Karpura, with its *Tikshna* and *Ushna* nature, exhibits strong *Kṛmighna*, *Stambhaka*, and *Shodhana* effects, helping to eliminate microbial load and internal toxins. *Shuddha Gandhaka* contributes to *Rasayana* and *Vranaropaka* actions, aiding tissue repair, especially in skin and metabolic disorders.

Shuddha Haratala, known for its *Kushtaghna*, *Lekhana*, and *Raktaprasadaka* properties, helps to cleanse the blood and reduce excessive *Kapha* and *Pitta* involvement. *Shuddha Vatsanabha*, when properly purified, acts as a *Vatahara*, *Jwaraghna*, and

Shoolahara, making it useful in managing colic pain, fevers, and neurological irritability. *Shuddha Jayapala*, with its strong *Virechaka* and *Bhedaka* qualities, facilitates effective *Shodhana*, clearing intestinal channels and supporting the removal of *Ama*.

The addition of *Triphala*, *Trikatu*, and *Mulaka* provides a herbal dimension to the formulation. These agents stimulate *Jatharagni*, support proper bowel function, and aid in *Medohara*, *Vatanulomana*, and *Shothahara* actions. *Gomutra*, used as *Bhavana Dravya*, enhances the *Srotoshodhana*, *Aamapachana*, and *Lekhana* effects of the overall formulation while also acting as a *Yogavahi*, enabling deeper tissue penetration and improved bioavailability.

Together, these components contribute to the multi-level action of *Rasachandrodaya* in addressing systemic imbalances. Based on its composition and traditional indications, the probable actions of *Rasachandrodaya* in key conditions are as follows:

1. ***Kushta***: *Rasachandrodaya* addresses the underlying *Rakta-Kapha dushti* and *Aamavisha* through its *Raktashodhaka*, *Lekhana*, and *Krimighna* properties. The presence of *Gandhaka*, *Haratala*, and *Triphala* aids in skin detoxification and healing, while *Shuddha Vatsanabha* helps manage pain, itching, and systemic inflammation.
2. ***Prameha***: The formulation improves *Agnibala*, reduces *Meda dhatu vriddhi*, and clears *Aama*, all of which are central to the pathology of *Prameha*. Ingredients like *Trikatu*, *Mulaka*, and *Gomutra* play a crucial role in regulating metabolism, facilitating weight reduction, and restoring proper *Mutravaha srotas* function.
3. ***Gulma***: *Rasachandrodaya* is indicated in *Gulma* due to its ability to pacify *Vata-Kapha*, break down *Aamavritta Vata*, and relieve *Srotorodha*. The *Lekhana*, *Shothahara*, and *Pachana* actions work together to reduce abdominal fullness, colic pain, and mass-like formations.
4. ***Jwara and Vishama Jwara***: The formulation acts on the root cause by digesting *Aama*, cleansing microchannels, and neutralizing *Visha* and *krimi*, which are often implicated in chronic and relapsing fevers. *Shuddha Vatsanabha* and *Jayapala* help bring down fever, while *Triphala* and *Trikatu* support immunity and digestion.
5. ***Shoola and Malajeerna***: *Rasachandrodaya* supports *Vatanulomana*, improves digestion, and eliminates undigested material, thereby reducing colic and bloating. Its *Tikshna*, *Ushna*, and *Katu* properties stimulate digestion and relieve stagnation in the *Annavaha* and *Purishavaha Srotas*.

6. **Visuchika and Sannipataja Vyadhi:** Through its robust *Shodhana*, *Aama Pachana*, and *Tridoshaghna* effects, *Rasachandrodaya* works effectively in clearing gastrointestinal toxins, correcting doshic imbalances, and stabilizing systemic functions, particularly in conditions marked by multiple dosha involvement.

CONCLUSION

Rasachandrodaya is a classical herbo-mineral formulation with multifaceted actions including *Aama Pachana*, *Srotoshodhaka*, *Tridosha Shamana*, and *Rasayana*. Its unique combination of *Rasoushadhis*, herbal powders, and *Gomutra* enhances its potency in managing chronic disorders such as *Kushta*, *Prameha*, *Gulma*, and *Jwara*. By addressing the root cause through *Agni Deepana*, detoxification, and doshic balance, *Rasachandrodaya* holds promise as an effective therapeutic agent in both classical and contemporary Ayurvedic practice.

REFERENCES

1. Sharma HP. *Rasayogasagara*. Vol. 2. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Krishnadas Academy, 2010; 260.
2. Sharma S. *Rasatarangini*. Hindi ed., commentary “Tarangini” by Devnath Singh Gautam. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Surbharati Prakashan; 2018. p. 105. 8th Taranga, Verses, 82–85.
3. Sharma S. *Rasatarangini*. Hindi ed., commentary “Tarangini” by Devnath Singh Gautam. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Surbharati Prakashan; 2018. p. 161. 8th Taranga, Verses, 1–3.
4. Sharma S. *Rasatarangini*. Hindi ed., commentary “Tarangini” by Devnath Singh Gautam. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Surbharati Prakashan; 2018. p. 105. 11th Taranga, Verse, 55.
5. Pandey G. *Dravyaguna Vijnana*. Vol. 3. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Krishnadas Academy, 2014; 824.
6. Sharma S. *Rasatarangini*. Hindi ed., commentary “Tarangini” by Devnath Singh Gautam. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Surbharati Prakashan; 2018. p. 105. 13th Taranga, Verse 81.
7. Sharma S. *Rasatarangini*. Edited by Pandit Kashinath Shastri. 11th ed. Delhi: Motilal Banarasidas Publication; 1979. 24th Taranga, Verse 5: 647.
8. Pandey G. *Dravyaguna Vijnana*. Vol. 1. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Krishnadas Academy; 2014; 102.
9. Pandey G. *Dravyaguna Vijnana*. Vol. 1. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Krishnadas Academy; 2014; 750.

10. Pandey G. *Dravyaguna Vijnana*. Vol. 1. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Krishnadas Academy; 2014; 366.
11. Pandey G. *Dravyaguna Vijnana*. Vol. 1. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Krishnadas Academy; 2014; 179.
12. Pandey G. *Dravyaguna Vijnana*. Vol. 3. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Krishnadas Academy; 2014; 116.
13. Pandey G. *Dravyaguna Vijnana*. Vol. 2. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Krishnadas Academy; 2014; 505.
14. *Ashtanga Hrudaya*, Sutra Sthana, Annaswarup Vigyaniya Adhyay. *Nirmala Hindi Commentary* by Tripathi B. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan; 2014. Verses 102: 108.
15. Agnivesha. *Charaka Samhita*, Pratisamskrita by Charaka. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Surbharati Prakashan; 2008. Sutrasthana, Chapter 8, Verse 142; 284.